

INFLUENCE OF THE LATIN LANGUAGE ON THE FORMATION OF MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7505947>

Abstract: This scientific article, in our opinion, has a weighty justification, it is designed to draw the attention of young specialists of higher and secondary medical level to the use of the basics of Latin and Greek in their work, to help teachers consolidate the understanding of students studying at various faculties of medical universities and colleges of the expediency of studying the subjects presented.

Key words: Latin language, medicine, dentistry, pediatrics, nursing, surgeon, science, medical terms, clinical terms, pharmaceutical terms.

Lingua Latina - or the Latin language. Linguistic direction of the language group Indo-European family, which got its name from the people of the Italic group (Italiks), a tribe Latins inhabiting the Italian province of Latium. Rome was the capital city of Latium. During the unification campaigns and military campaigns of the kings and emperors of the Roman Republic, and then and empire, along with the borders of the state, culture and linguistic influence gradually spread

After the accession of the Greek policies to the composition of the empire (in the II century BC), the linguistic assimilation and corresponding linguistic (rhetorical) exchange of Latin and Greek languages. The Latin language showed the continuity of the Greek medical and pharmaceutical (alchemical) terminology, having largely enriched its vocabulary with new concepts and the structures of the medical glossary of Hippocrates.

In the course of history, the Greek terms used Roman medicus ordinarius - state doctors and their military counterparts Archiatrs "Archiatri" acquired a Latinized form, for example: os coxae - pelvic bone, cranium - skull, vena, ae - vein, arteria, ae - artery. But, despite the assimilation of the language, some terms have retained their original Greek forms and endings, for example: apnoë - lack of breath, dyspnoë - violation breath (shortness of breath), anuria - lack of urine, albumen - protein, albuminuria - protein in the urine.

Latin and ancient Greek have been languages for centuries international medical community: anatomical nomenclature, diagnoses and symptoms

diseases, pharmacological and chemical products, etc. Their common terminology is based on fundamental foundations of the two original languages, now combined into a single glossary of Latin medical terms.

So, with the advent of the new medical discipline "Dentistry", the Latin language acquires new terms related to dental auxiliary instruments, cavity diseases mouth, as well as ways to treat them. Examples: gingivitis gingivitis is an inflammation of the mucous membrane of the gums.

It is extremely problematic to imagine modern medical education without mastering the basic in Latin terms. Learning the basics of the Latin language is of tremendous importance in teaching and training of a qualified medical specialist of middle and senior level, since helps to consciously assimilate and perceive the medical terms of Latin and Greek backgrounds that the future professional will encounter throughout his practical activities. The following Latin proverb has been known to physicians since ancient times: "Invia est in medicina via sine lingua Latina" - The path to medicine is impassable without the Latin language. We dare

to assure that this thesis is objective to this day.

The main outcome of the study: the education of a professionally competent medical and a pharmaceutical worker who owns the basic knowledge base Latin, allowing you to easily transfer information about the diseases of patients in the international medical language, while maintaining confidentiality information for non-health workers.

We have carried out empirical research based on familiarization with scientific works on medical ethics, clinical medicine and history medicine. Interest in this work was aroused in our research group by the question: why the Latin language, although belonging to the category of so-called "dead languages", is still widely studied in all secondary and higher professional medical institutions?

The search for answers to the question of interest to us drew our attention to the study treatises of various figures of various scientific fields. We have studied the works including issues of the history of medicine, philosophy, medical ethics and medical psychology.

From the accumulated and studied information, we managed to derive theoretical substantiation of the need to use the Latin language in various medical areas of activity. For example, modern medical Latin is widely used in various clinical studies, in cases where one Latin term allows you to express a

huge range of information needed by the doctor for quick recognition of the location and nature of the disease, which in turn allows the doctor save valuable time and build an appropriate treatment plan for the patient.

As example, let's consider the terms used in general medical practice, paying attention to focus on selected terms from abdominal surgery and urology: peritonitis-derived from peritoneum - peritoneum and ending - itis - inflammation, which is a single the term can be described as "inflammation of the parietal and visceral sheets peritoneum, which is accompanied by a severe general condition of the body.

Consider the term anuria, where the prefix an is negation, and urina is urine, where the joint meaning of the term can be represented as "a complete cessation of the flow of urine into the bladder against the background of failure to excrete this biological fluid by the kidneys, or its failure to enter the urinary bubble". Or, for example, glomerulonephritis, where glomerulus is a glomerulus and nephros is a kidney, -itis - inflammation, which means "inflammation of the renal glomeruli." Based on given examples, we can see that the knowledge of scientific medical terminology saves the doctor's time and allows you to respond to complaints in the shortest possible time patient and develop an appropriate treatment strategy.

Based on the writings on medical ethics, our research team has identified such component of medicine, as the preservation of medical secrecy. The first rule to be remember the young physician still sounds in Latin "Primum non nocere" – which means “do no harm”, so, for example, a medical council that makes its decision on a particular disease that threatens or possibly threatens the life of the patient, uses Latin terminology in his speech, accessible to the understanding of the members Medical College and leaving a veil of secrecy for the understanding of civil layman.

In summary, our research team concluded that medicine and the Latin language are inextricably linked and go hand in hand, even after many centuries of coexistence. It would be correct to point out the fact that the knowledge of a physician who does not speak Latin is at least incomplete.

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